

Eligibility Criteria: Carpentries Instructor Training Seats — Call 1

Building digital skills training and lesson development capacity in the Netherlands NES domain (DC4NES) Project | 2026

About the DC4NES project

The DC4NES project builds digital skills training capacity in the Netherlands. It is funded by TDCC-NES and runs for two years, starting in December 2025. The project funds 50 Carpentries Instructor Training seats across two calls. Call 1 (October 2026 training) will offer 30-35 seats; Call 2 (February 2027 training) will offer the remaining seats.

Becoming a certified Carpentries Instructor enables you to teach foundational coding and data science workshops at your institution and beyond. The training is conducted in English by Carpentries Instructor Trainers, on location in the Netherlands. Candidates who are unable to attend in person may participate in an alternative online session. Each seat is valued at approximately EUR 900. Certified instructors are expected to teach at least two Carpentries workshops within two years of completing their certification.

Eligibility: Call 1 (open 4 March – 29 May 2026) — Institutional nomination

Call 1 is open to any Dutch research-performing organisation that does not currently hold a Carpentries membership that includes Instructor Training seats. Candidates must be nominated by their institution; self-nominations are not permitted. Institutions are responsible for nominating candidates in a fair and transparent manner, ensuring that the selection process is open to all eligible staff and free from bias or preferential treatment.

Individuals interested in applying should contact their institutional DCC or equivalent research data support unit. A second call will be announced in September 2026 and will be open to individual applications.

The following institutions are currently holding a Carpentries membership:

- University of Amsterdam
- TU Delft
- University of Twente
- Leiden University
- Netherlands eScience Center
- Tilburg University
- Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
- DCC-PO (Research Support for Universities of Applied Sciences)
- NWO-I (AMOLF, ARCNL, ASTRON, CWI, DIFFER, Nikhef, NIOZ, NSCR, SRON)

The following research-performing institutions did not have a Carpentries membership and are eligible to nominate candidates:

- Eindhoven University of Technology
- Wageningen University & Research
- Maastricht University
- Radboud University
- University of Groningen
- Utrecht University
- Dutch Caribbean Universities
- Naturalis
- SURF
- KNMI (Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute)
- KNAW Institutes (DANS, Netherlands Institute for Neuroscience, NIOO-KNAW, WI-KNAW)
- TNO
- ARCNL (Advanced Research Centre for NanoLithography)
- TO2 Federation (Deltares, MARIN, NLR)
- RIVM (National Institute of Public Health and the Environment)
- IHE Delft Institute for Water Education

Note: Although members of 4TU which have a Carpentries membership, Wageningen University and TU Eindhoven are eligible as they do not currently have Instructor Training seats.

Of the 50 seats in Call 1 and Call 2 combined, at least 50% are reserved for candidates affiliated with an NES domain or NES-affiliated department. The remaining seats are open to candidates from other research domains.

Each eligible institution may nominate 1–2 candidates. A nominated candidate must meet all of the following criteria:

- Be affiliated with the nominating institution.
- Be active in the NES domain as a researcher, research support professional (data steward or research software trainer), or data/software engineer.
- Is not already a certified Carpentries Instructor.
- Commit to teaching a minimum of two Carpentries workshops within two years of completing certification.

General notes

- This call is open to candidates regardless of contract type (permanent or temporary). The project aims for at least 50% of all trained instructors to hold permanent contracts and at least 25% for temporary staff; contract type will be taken into account in more detail in Call 2.

Related documents

You can find all related documents in the Digital Capacity for NES community on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/dc4nes>

- Selection Criteria: Carpentries Instructor Training Seats — Call 1
- Selection Process: Carpentries Instructor Training Seats — Call 1